

Entity Selection Profile entity attribute

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Motivation

Federation operators have rules for entity registration to ensure a good user experience within that federation. These rules are typically published in a Metadata Registration Practice Statement. When we look at a wider ecosystem where multiple federation operators register SPs and IdPs, we need prioritization and selection rules. The rule that many people know about is the metadata combination rule in eduGAIN metadata aggregation, which enforces unique entityIDs.

However, unique entityIDs are not sufficient to provide a good user experience for IdP discovery in an ecosystem. Accurate and complete metadata (such as DisplayName and logos) will help people select the appropriate IdP when logging in, although this still requires an individual to make the correct choice at login time. What if there was also a mechanism in metadata for an SP to describe which IdPs it would prefer to interoperate with? This Entity Selection Profile aims to provide that.

Building on earlier work from SeamlessAccess, we are developing a profile that can allow SPs to identify a set of IdPs, either by entityID or generically by registrationAuthority or entity attribute. They coined the term "trustinfo" although we're realising it's actually an entity selection profile.

The first step is to define an entity attribute as a container for transporting selection rules and profiles. This step focusses on the current SAML environment.

There is supporting material in the REFEDS wiki on the Working Group page [WG]

XML namespaces and prefixes

Conventional namespace prefixes are used:

Namespace prefix	Namespace	Reference
md:	urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:2.0:metadata	SAML2Meta
mdattr:	urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:metadata:attributes	MetaAttr

Definitions

The Entity Selection Profile is an entity attribute which contains filtering rules in support of IdP discovery. These filtering rules allow SP owners and others to define selection rules for which IdPs to display in a discovery service. The entity attribute has Name="https://refeds.org/entity-selection-profile" and NameFormat="urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:2.0:attrname-format:uri".

Syntax

- The entity attribute is found in md:EntityDescriptor/md:Extensions/mdattr:EntityAttributes. We recognise that the Entity Attributes specification allows md:EntitiesDescriptor/md:Extensions/md:EntityAttributes elements, but we rule them out for operational and conceptual reasons.
- There is only one instance of an Entity Selection Profile entity attribute in an entity. Behaviour when more than one is present is not defined by this profile.
- Composition with other sources of filtering is not defined by this profile.
- The value of the entity attribute is Base64 encoded [Base64].
- Syntax of the decoded value is defined by the metadata consumer.
- Any whitespace before, after or internal to the value must be ignored.

Semantics

- The expected consumer of the entity attribute is a discovery service. Federation operators and entity operators are not expected to decode the value.
- Semantics of the decoded value are defined by the

metadata consumer.

- We recommend that null values, incorrectly encoded values or other errors are treated as if there was no filtering. We do not recommend that the whole entity metadata is considered invalid.
- If the decoded value does not conform to the requirements of the consumer, we recommend that the consumer assumes there is no filtering. We do not recommend that the entity metadata is considered invalid.

Registration criteria

Any entity that has a SP role can register this entity attribute.

Examples

This example contains JSON which defines profiles for filtering in SeamlessAccess. Other discovery services may use different Base64-encoded syntax for their filtering rules.

```
<mdattr:EntityAttributes>
<saml:Attribute
NameFormat="urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:2.0:attrname-format:uri"
Name="https://refeds.org/entity-selection-profile">
<saml:AttributeValue>
eyJwcm9maWxlcyI6eyJzd2FtaWQtb25seSI6eyJzdHJpY3QiOnRydWUsIm
VudGI0aWVzIjpbeyJzZWxIY3QiOiJodHRwOi8vd3d3LnN3YW1pZC5zZS8iL
CjtYXRjaCI6InJlZ2lzdHJhdGlvbkF1dGhvcmI0eSI6ImluY2x1ZGUiOnRydW
V9XX0sImVkdWdhaW4iOnsiZW50aXRpZXMlOlt7ImluY2x1ZGUlOmZhbH
NlLCJtYXRjaCI6InJlZ2lzdHJhdGlvbkF1dGhvcmI0eSI6InNlbGVjdCI6Imh0d
HBzOi8vb3BlbmF0aGVucy5uZXQifV0sInN0cmIjdCI6IHRydWV9fX0=
</saml:AttributeValue>
</saml:Attribute>
</mdattr:EntityAttributes>
```

The filtering rule is {"profiles":{"swamid-only":{"strict":true,"entities":[{"select":"https://www.swamid.se/","match":"registrationAuthority","include":true}]},"edugain":{"entities":[{"include":false,"match":"registrationAuthority","select":"https://openathens.net"}],"strict": true}}}

This non-functional example has an entity attribute with no value

The metadata consumer should ignore the attribute and perform no filtering.

```
<mdattr:EntityAttributes>
  <saml:Attribute
    NameFormat="urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:2.0:attrname-format:uri"
    Name="https://refeds.org/entity-selection-profile">
    <saml:AttributeValue />
  </saml:Attribute>
</mdattr:EntityAttributes>
```

This non-functional example contains a space

The metadata consumer should ignore the attribute and perform no filtering.

```
<mdattr:EntityAttributes>
  <saml:Attribute
    NameFormat="urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:2.0:attrname-format:uri"
    Name="https://refeds.org/entity-selection-profile">
    <saml:AttributeValue> </saml:AttributeValue>
  </saml:Attribute>
</mdattr:EntityAttributes>
```

This non-functional example contains an incorrectly encoded value

The metadata consumer should ignore the attribute and perform no filtering.

```
<mdattr:EntityAttributes>
  <saml:Attribute
    NameFormat="urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:2.0:attrname-format:uri"
    Name="https://refeds.org/entity-selection-profile">
    <saml:AttributeValue>*</saml:AttributeValue>
  </saml:Attribute>
</mdattr:EntityAttributes>
```

Security considerations

to be determined

References

- [SAML2Meta] "OASIS Standard, Metadata for the OASIS Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML)", V2.0. March 2005. <https://docs.oasis-open.org/security/saml/v2.0/saml-metadata-2.0-os.pdf>.
- [MetaAttr] Scott Cantor et al. "SAML V2.0 Metadata Extension for Entity Attributes Version 1.0". 4 August 2009. <https://docs.oasis-open.org/security/saml/Post2.0/sstc-metadata-attr-cs-01.pdf>.
- [Base64] "The Base16, Base32, and Base64 Data Encodings". RFC 4648. <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc4648>.
- [WG] REFEDS wiki page for the working group. <https://wiki.refeds.org/display/GROUPS/SeamlessAccess+Trustinfo+Metadata+Working+Group>.